

Original Article

BARRIERS AND STRATEGIES FOR INCREASING IMMUNIZATION UPTAKE AMONG NURSING MOTHERS ATTENDING ANTENATAL CLINIC IN PUBLIC HOSPITALS IN ENUGU STATE

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Abstract

The study examined the barriers and practice of strategies for increasing immunization uptake among nursing mothers attending antenatal clinic in public hospitals in Enugu State. Two research questions and two hypotheses guided the study. Descriptive survey research design was used for the study. The population for the study consisted of five hundred and fifty two (552) nursing mothers in public hospitals in Enugu State. The sample for this study consisted of one hundred and sixty six (166) nursing mothers gotten through the use of Taro Yamene (1964) formula. Simple random sampling techniques was applied to get the sample for the study. A Structured questionnaire titled 'Barriers and Practice of Strategies for Increasing Uptake of Immunization (BPSIUIQ)' was the instrument for data collection. The instrument was validated by three experts, two from the Department of Human Kinetics and Health Education and one from the Department of Science and Computer all from ESUT. The reliability of the instrument was established by employing Cronbach's Alpha statistic which yielded .79 reliability index showing that the instrument was reliable. The researcher administered the questionnaires directly to the respondents with the help of three research assistants. Data collected was analyzed using mean and standard deviation while the hypotheses were tested using t-test at 0.05 level of significance. The finding of the study revealed among others that; that lack of awareness about the importance of immunization, cultural belief, inadequate information, financial constraints, poor vaccine supply and misinformation are barriers to increasing uptake of immunization among nursing mothers, the practice of strategies for increase in immunization uptake among nursing mothers attending immunization services in public hospital in Enugu State was to a low extent. It was concluded that a lot of factors pose problem to increasing uptake of immunization among nursing mothers and also the practice of strategies for increasing immunization uptake among nursing mothers attending immunization services in public hospital in Enugu State was to a low extent. It was recommended among others that government should organize workshop and seminar on immunization where its importance should be explained for the nursing mothers.

Keywords: *Barriers, practice of strategies, immunization uptake, nursing mother*

Introduction

Throughout history, avoidable illnesses have had a profound influence on people, often with disastrous consequences. However, World Health Organization (2021), posited that the introduction of immunization transformed public health, allowing communities to minimize, if not eliminate, the burden of infectious illnesses. According to the Nigeria Centre for Disease Control (2021), immunization is an important part of public health strategy for avoiding vaccine-preventable illnesses including measles, poliomyelitis, and hepatitis B, which continue to impact children and vulnerable communities. This means that immunization is the process of protecting an individual from infectious illnesses by the use of vaccinations. The history of immunization may be traced back to the late 18th century, when Edward Jenner created the first effective smallpox vaccine, conferring protection with cowpox material (Simmons, 2019). Following Jenner's ground-breaking discovery, the nineteenth century saw the development of vaccinations for a variety of illnesses, including rabies and anthrax, laying the groundwork for contemporary immunology. Mass immunization programs in the twentieth century significantly lowered disease incidence, as seen by the eradication of smallpox in 1980 and the near-eradication of polio in many places (World Health Organisation, 2021). Despite these advances, vaccination hesitancy and misinformation remain significant concerns, emphasizing the need for continual education and public health measures especially among infants.

Immunization protects infants from a variety of dangerous illnesses, including measles, mumps, rubella, diphtheria, tetanus, and pertussis. CDC (2023) noted that vaccines such as the Tetanus, Diphtheria, and Pertussis (whooping cough) (DTaP), Measle, Mumps and Rubella (German measles)(MMR), and Routine Immunization Body System (HIBS) series considerably lower the

occurrence of these infections, which can cause serious consequences or death if not treated on time. Supporting this assertion, World Health Organization (2023) emphasizes vaccines' usefulness in preventing hospitalizations and establishing community immunity against epidemics. In addition, Centre for Disease Control and Prevention (2023), found that increased immunization coverage has helped to prevent the reappearance of previously controlled illnesses. WHO (2019), reported that globally, immunization efforts have considerably reduced the prevalence of illnesses such as measles, which killed over 140,000 people in 2018, mostly unvaccinated children. United Nations Children's Fund, UNICEF (2022), further reveals that vaccination coverage is different across different regions in Africa and areas with low immunization rates may experience increased morbidity and mortality due to illnesses that could have been prevented by vaccination.

In Nigeria, National Primary Health Care Development Agency, NPHCDA (2022), reports that immunization programmes have had a significant impact on disease prevalence, with over 20,000 occurrences of infantile paralysis documented prior to the introduction of the polio vaccine. The report also states that routine immunization coverage in Nigeria is around 57%, with large regional differences. UNICEF (2023), revealed that although efforts were made to boost vaccine outreach, there are still some states that continue to face hurdles due to conflicts and logistical concerns impeding immunization programmes.

These statistics shows that immunization is very essential in prevention of diseases as the prevalence of most illness reduces when individual especially nursing mothers to ensure that their child is immunized against diseases. However, despite the relevance of immunization to the health of children it appears as if the rate of immunization is low in Enugu State. This assertion was affirmed by

National Primary Health Care Development Agency, (NPHCDA) (2022), which found that immunization rates among nursing mothers in Nigeria are varied, with national statistics showing that only roughly 57% of infants under one year received all basic immunizations. These reports highlights that while there has been progress owing to increasing public health efforts, total coverage of immunization among nursing mothers remains below intended levels, indicating that many children continue to skip crucial immunizations (Nigeria Centre for Disease Control, 2021). Hence this study examines the barriers to immunization and practice of the strategies for increasing immunization rate among nursing mothers in Enugu State.

Barriers refer to limitations that hinder an individual from doing something. In this study barriers to uptake of immunization among nursing mothers refer to factors that prevent nursing mothers from ensuring that their children is adequately protected against diseases through vaccination. Umar, Abdullahi and Lawal (2021), revealed that there are numerous barriers to immunization among nursing mothers which includes misinformation and lack of understanding about vaccine advantages. This submission specifically highlights that some nursing mothers may believe vaccination myths or they may be unaware of the existence of vaccination programme or the effectiveness of vaccination in prevention of diseases and these may be among the barriers to uptake of vaccination among nursing mothers. Adeleke and Adebayo (2020), adds that cultural practices and beliefs are also important factors that should be evaluated to determine if it is a barrier to uptake of immunization because some groups of nursing mothers may prefer traditional medicine to immunization. Furthermore, it is not surprising that Nigerian healthcare faces structural factors such as inadequate healthcare facilities and a lack of outreach initiatives which may impede access to immunization services. Moreover, Ogunfowokan and Ogunbiyi (2021), found that

socioeconomic variables such as poverty and a lack of mobility options contribute considerably to low adoption rates. Nevertheless, it is inconclusive if these factors are among the barriers to uptake of immunization among nursing mothers attending antenatal clinic in public hospitals in Enugu State thus the need for this study.

It is worthy to note that several strategies for increasing immunization uptake among nursing mothers in Nigeria have been proposed based on previous research. According to Adediran, Adeoye and Bamidele (2022), introducing community-based health education interventions can greatly increase knowledge and dispel myths about immunization among nursing mothers. In addition, Okafor, Eze and Ukaegbu (2023), opined that using mobile health technology to provide reminders and vaccination schedules can increase attendance at immunization sites. Healthcare systems must be strengthened by ensuring that healthcare staffs are appropriately prepared to give immunization services and successfully interact with mothers.

Nursing mother is a woman who is breastfeeding her baby A nursing mother is a woman who gave birth and is actively seeking medical advice for herself and her infant (WHO,2021). Nursing mothers is the focus of this study because they most likely handling the pressures of parenting while also ensuring her child obtain proper healthcare and vaccines. In addition, the educational backgrounds of a nursing mother have a substantial impact on their awareness and perception of immunization barriers, as well as the methods required to overcome them. According to Aluoch and Okafor, 2022; and Oyejide and Alimba (2021), women with higher educational backgrounds have better health literacy, which corresponds with more favourable attitudes towards immunization and the capacity to efficiently navigate health systems. On the other hand, Eze, Eze and Okafor (2023), reported that lower educational attainment often results in misconceptions about vaccine safety and efficacy, thereby impacting their

willingness to vaccinate their children. Moreover, despite some results on immunization obstacles, gaps in the research exist, notably in the context of Enugu State. Previous research frequently generalized findings throughout Nigeria without taking into consideration local cultural practices and socioeconomic factors (Okafor, Eze & Ukaegbu, 2023). Furthermore, there is insufficient qualitative study on nursing mothers' barriers and strategies for increasing uptake of immunization in public hospitals (Nwankwo & Okwuosa, 2022). This lack of study in barriers to immunization and strategies to immunization uptake necessitated this study especially among nursing mothers attending postnatal clinic in public hospital in Enugu State. It is against this background that this study examines the barriers and strategies for increasing immunization uptake among nursing mothers attending antenatal clinic in public hospitals in Enugu State.

Statement of the Problem

Based on the relevance of immunization, it was expected that nursing women visiting prenatal clinics in public hospitals in Enugu State, Nigeria, would have easy access to complete immunization services, health care practitioners ought to engage in proactive education activities, ensuring that mothers are well educated about the advantages of vaccines and encouraged to include them into their child's health routine. Moreover, the healthcare system is expected to be adequately resourced, ensuring that vaccinations are easily accessible, appropriately kept, and delivered by skilled experts in a supportive setting.

However, the research observed that there are major hurdles to immunization among nursing mothers who visit prenatal clinics in public hospitals in Enugu State. Many mothers confront issues as a result of a lack of awareness and understanding of immunization regimens and the relevance of vaccination for their infants. Socioeconomic problems such as poverty and illiteracy seem to

impede access to immunization services, leaving some mothers unable to navigate the healthcare system successfully. Furthermore, disinformation about immunizations spreads across the community, leading to skepticism and opposition to vaccinations. As a result, many nursing women may postpone or entirely skip necessary vaccines for their infants.

Thus the study examines barriers and strategies for increasing immunization among nursing mothers attending antenatal clinic in public hospitals in Enugu State.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study is to investigate the barriers and extent of practice of strategies for increasing immunization uptake among nursing mother's postnatal clinic in public hospitals in Enugu State. Specifically, the study sought to;

1. determine the barriers to uptake of immunization among nursing mothers attending postnatal clinic in public hospitals in Enugu State
2. ascertain the extent the strategies for increasing uptake of immunization among nursing mothers attending postnatal clinic in public hospitals in Enugu State

Research Questions

The following research questions guided this study:

1. What are the barriers to uptake of immunization among nursing mothers attending postnatal clinic in public hospitals in Enugu State?
2. What are the strategies for increasing uptake of immunization among nursing mothers attending postnatal clinic in public hospitals in Enugu State?

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference in the mean response score of educated and less educated nursing mothers attending postnatal clinic in public hospitals in Enugu State on the barriers to uptake of immunization among nursing mothers.
2. There is no significant difference in the mean response scores of educated and less educated nursing mothers attending postnatal clinic in public

hospitals in Enugu State on the extent of practice of strategies for increasing uptake of immunization.

Methods

The study employed descriptive survey design. The population for the study consisted of five hundred and fifty two (552) nursing mothers attending postnatal clinic in public hospitals in Enugu State. The sample for this study consisted of one hundred and sixty six (166) nursing mothers, which was determined with the use of Taro Yamane (1964) formula. Purposive stratified and proportionate random sampling techniques sampling technique were employed to obtain the sample.

The instrument that was used for data collection was a structured and validated questionnaire titled “Barriers and Practice of Strategies for Increasing Uptake of Immunization Questionnaire (BSUIQ)”. The questionnaire has two sections, A and B. Section A seeks to elicit information on socio-demographic variables of respondents. Section B has two cluster based on barriers and strategies for improving uptake of immunization among nursing mothers attending postnatal clinic in public hospitals in Enugu State. Cluster one had ten items on barriers to uptake of immunization among nursing mothers attending postnatal clinic in public hospitals in Enugu State, while cluster two had ten items on practice of strategies for improving uptake of immunization among nursing mothers attending antenatal clinic in public hospitals in Enugu State. The questionnaire has twenty (20) items in all. For barriers, the respondents were given response option of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD). In the second research question, the respondents were given an option of Very High Extent (VHE), High Extent (GE), Low Extent (LE), and Very Low Extent (VLE). The Questionnaire was validated by three experts; two from the Department of Human Kinetics and Health Education and one from Department of Mathematics and Computer Education, with specialization in Measurement and

Evaluation, all in the Faculty of Education, Enugu State University of Science and Technology (ESUT). The reliability of the instrument was established by carrying out a trial test by administering with 20 copies of the questionnaire on twenty (20) nursing mothers in public hospitals in Abia State. Consequently, Cronbach’s Alpha statistic was employed and the reliability coefficient (r) of 0.77 and 0.83 were obtained for the two clusters of the instrument. Consequently, reliability coefficient alpha level of 0.89 was obtained for the entire instrument.

The researcher visited the sampled public hospitals and administered the questionnaires directly to the respondents with the help of three research assistants. However after data collection, it was found that 9 copies of the questionnaire were filled incorrectly. Thus only 157 copies of the questionnaire (educated 124, less educated 33,) were correctly filled and qualified to be used for data analysis, giving a 95% return rate. Data was analyzed using mean and standard deviation while the hypotheses were tested using t-test at 0.05 level of significance. The decision rule was as follows; for barrier to immunization uptake mean of 2.5 and above means barrier, while mean below 2.5 is not barrier. For practice of strategies for immunization uptake, mean 2.5 and above means great extent while mean below 2.5 means low extent. For hypotheses, when the calculated p-value was equal or greater than level of significance (0.05), the null hypotheses were not rejected. On the other hand, when the p-value was less than level of significance (0.05) the null hypotheses were rejected.

Result

Research Question 1:

What are the barriers to increasing immunization uptake among nursing mothers attending antenatal clinic in public hospitals in Enugu State?

Table 1:
Mean and Standard Deviation Scores of Respondents on the barriers to increasing immunization uptake among nursing mothers attending antenatal clinic n = 157

S/N	Barriers to increase uptake of immunization among nursing mothers attending antenatal clinic;	Educated \bar{X}_1	SD ₁	Less Educated \bar{X}_2	SD ₂	Overall \bar{X}_G	SD _G	Deci
1	Lack of awareness about the importance of immunization.	3.05	0.58	2.79	1.30	2.92	0.94	A
2	Cultural beliefs and misconceptions about vaccines.	3.45	0.63	2.52	1.10	2.99	0.87	A
3	Limited access to healthcare facilities.	3.34	1.05	1.64	0.77	2.49	0.91	D
4	Long waiting times at clinics.	3.87	0.47	3.00	1.07	3.44	0.77	A
5	Inadequate information from healthcare providers.	2.99	0.47	2.52	1.10	2.76	0.79	A
6	Fear of side effects from vaccines.	3.45	0.77	1.52	0.50	2.49	0.64	D
7	Financial constraints for transportation and consultation fees.	3.11	0.43	2.06	1.05	2.59	0.74	A
8	Poor vaccine supply and stockouts.	3.46	0.65	2.88	0.81	3.17	0.73	A
9	Misinformation spread through social media.	3.18	0.76	2.52	1.10	2.85	0.93	A
10	Lack of support from family and community.	2.82	0.87	1.52	0.50	2.17	0.69	D

Key = A- Agree; D- Disagree; SD- Standard Deviation; Deci- Decision

The data in table 1 above show that majority of the items (i.e. item 1, 2, 4, 5, 7, 8 and 9) are barriers to uptake of immunization. This is shown by their mean values which ranges from 2.55 to 3.44. On the other hand, the remaining items (i.e. items 3, 6 and 10) indicates none barriers to immunization uptake. It then means that lack of awareness about the

importance, cultural belief, inadequate information, financial constraints, poor vaccine supply and misinformation are barriers to increasing uptake of immunization.

Research Question 2:

What is the extent of practice of strategies for increasing immunization uptake among nursing mothers attending antenatal clinic in public hospitals in Enugu State?

Table 2:
Mean and Standard Deviation Scores of Respondents on the Extent of Practice of Strategies for Increasing Immunization among Nursing Mothers n = 157

S/N	Items	Educated \bar{X}	N =124 SD ₁	Less Educated \bar{X}	N = 33M L SD ₂	Over all \bar{X}	SD	Deci
11	healthcare personnel educating mothers on the benefits of immunization increases immunization	3.29	0.92	1.52	0.50	2.41	0.71	LE
12	Providing effective communication with mothers about available vaccination.	3.05	0.44	2.06	0.74	2.56	0.59	HE
13	healthcare personnel conducting home visit to nursing mothers can increase vaccination	3.02	0.47	1.64	0.77	2.33	0.62	LE
14	Reducing waiting times for vaccination administration.	1.49	1.03	1.64	0.77	1.57	0.90	LE
15	Providing transportation support for nursing mothers.	3.11	0.43	1.52	0.50	2.32	0.47	LE
16	offering free vaccination programme	3.13	0.42	2.52	1.08	2.83	0.75	HE
17	using mobile clinics to reach remote areas can bridge distance barrier	3.26	0.47	1.00	0.00	2.13	0.24	LE
18	organizing community immunization with the support of local community leaders	3.02	0.60	1.00	0.00	2.01	0.30	LE
19	Offering incentives for mothers who vaccinate their children.	2.92	0.65	1.64	0.77	2.28	0.71	LE
20	Utilizing social media to spread accurate information about immunization.	2.82	0.87	2.76	1.16	2.79	1.02	HE

Cluster Mean/ SD 2.91 0.63 1.73 0.63 2.32 0.63 LE

Key = HE- High Extent; LE- Low Extent; SD- Standard Deviation; Deci- Decision

The data in Table 2 above shows that out of 10 items for determining the extent of practice of strategies for improving uptake of immunization, only 3 items (ie items 12, 16, and 20) have a value above 2.50 while the remaining items have a value below 2.50. The overall or grand mean is 2.32

indicating that the practice of the strategies for increase in immunization uptake was to a low extent.

Hypotheses

H01

There is no significant difference in the mean response scores of educated and less educated nursing mothers attending antenatal clinic in public hospitals in Enugu State on the barriers to increasing immunization.

Table 3:

Summary of t-test Analysis of Difference Between the Response of Educated and Less Educated Nursing Mothers Attending Antenatal Clinic in Public Hospitals in Enugu State on the Barriers to Uptake of Immunization

Variables	N	Mean	Df	P-value	Decision
Educated	124	3.27	155	0.01	Reject Ho
Less Educated	33	2.30			

Table 3 above shows that the calculated p-value (0.01) was less than 0.05 level of significance. This means that the null hypothesis was rejected, or that it is significant. It then shows that there was significant difference in the mean response scores of educated and less educated nursing mothers attending antenatal clinic in public hospitals in

Enugu State on the barriers to increasing immunization.

H02

There is no significant difference in the mean response scores of educated and less educated nursing mothers attending postnatal clinic in public hospitals in Enugu State on the extent of practice of strategies for increasing uptake of immunization.

Table 4:

Summary of t-test analysis of Difference Between the Response of Educated and Less Educated Nursing Mothers Attending Postnatal Clinic in Public Hospitals in Enugu State on the Strategies for Increasing Immunization

Variables	N	X	SD	Df	P-value	Decision
Educated	124	2.91	0.63	155	0.52	Accept Ho
Less Educated	33	1.73	0.63			

Table 4 above showed that the calculated p-value (0.52) is above 0.05 level of significance. This means that the null hypothesis is accepted or that it is not significant. It then shows that there was no

significant difference in the mean response scores of educated and less educated nursing mothers attending postnatal clinic in public hospitals in

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Enugu State on the extent of practice of strategies for increasing immunization uptake..

Discussion of Findings

Finding revealed that lack of awareness about the importance of immunization, cultural belief, inadequate information, financial constraints, poor vaccine supply and misinformation are barriers to increasing uptake of immunization among nursing mothers attending antenatal clinic in public hospitals in Enugu State. The findings align with those of Adediran, Adeoye, and Bamidele (2022), which indicated that the obstacles are multifaceted and necessitate targeted interventions to address these challenges. Thus mothers' readiness to vaccinate their children is significantly influenced by misconceptions regarding vaccines and a deficiency of trust in healthcare professionals. Adeleke and Adebayo (2020), contested this finding, claiming that some women may lack a complete understanding of the need of immunization due to inadequate health education. Therefore, improving health literacy and increasing awareness can substantially reduce perceived obstacles. This perspective asserts that enhancing educational programs may be more effective than simply blaming failures on existing obstacles, hence highlighting the possibilities of a proactive approach that prioritizes education over merely identifying issues. The researcher acknowledges the substantial influence of personal and systemic barriers, emphasizing that their resolution requires a comprehensive understanding of individual experiences and community circumstances.

Finding revealed that the strategies for increase in immunization uptake among nursing mothers attending immunization services in public hospital in Enugu State was to a low extent. This finding was not expected bearing in mind the importance of immunization to children especially new born.

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However this study was in agreement with other research finding such as Umar, Abdullahi, and Lawal (2021) which revealed that many public health projects in Nigeria suffer from ineffective implementation due to low funding, insufficient staff training, and minimal community engagement. This observation aligns with the study's findings, which indicated a systematic failure in the planning and execution of effective public health programs. The study indicated that the absence of robust tactics has resulted in ambiguous communications regarding the significance of vaccinations, leaving mothers uncertain about the advantages and necessity of immunization. The researcher believes that there is need for additional participatory strategies that incorporate feedback from the mothers themselves. This can facilitate the development of programs that are more pertinent, culturally attuned, and efficacious.

Recommendations

The researcher recommends that;

1. The government should organize workshop and seminar on immunization where its importance should be explained for the nursing mothers. There is need to establish community outreach programs to educate nursing mothers about the importance of immunization, addressing cultural misconceptions and providing reliable information regarding vaccination schedules and health benefits.
2. There is need to advocate for improved healthcare resources at antenatal clinics, including training for healthcare providers on the significance of immunizations and ensuring the availability of vaccines, thus removing logistical barriers to access.
3. Also, the government should adopt mobile health (mHealth) technology to deliver immunization information to bridge the awareness and access gaps especially in remote areas

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